

Radical Creativities

by Lorenzo Biferale *

* PhD
Candidate,
GSSI, L'Aquila,
Italy

With Radical Creativities, we seek to provide a platform for the stories and experiences of people and organisations which consider the cultural as necessary to achieve the just and equitable transformation of communities, manifesting this ambition through action. We believe that creative and cultural practices have an intrinsically transformative value, and that this value spills over into the communities that are both object and subject of these practices.

Radical Creativities will welcome diverse voices from all backgrounds, embracing the expressive use of different languages and media. Radical Creativities proudly embraces plurality as the only way to understand the complexity that surrounds us, to make it our own and to respect it with our actions. In the project's name, we use 'Creativity' in the plural, emphasising the need to legitimise different practices and histories, bringing them together and letting them mutually contaminate each other. Academic research, cultural practice and art are not three separate worlds, but rather different ways to interpret, understand and assimilate the same reality. Through these three lenses, we explore who we are as communities across time and space, in permanent transition.

The radical creativities presented within the project will therefore have different sources; they will be told by artists, researchers, designers, curators and anyone who

makes their cultural action a transformative one. Mediums will be multiple; research papers, photos, videos, works of art or any form that best conveys the author's process of exploration and transformation.

The voices will be radical because they are deeply rooted in the present, in its analysis and understanding. These are the voices that find meaning in addressing the contradictions they observe, navigating complexity with nuance in order to transform the way we inhabit our communities.

This pilot issue seeks to be the manifesto of Radical Creativities, bringing together multiple voices in different formats. The contributions address two main themes; on the one hand, the link between cultural and collective practices, and on the other, the transformative role and social impact of culture and creativity. The two topics are explored through different practices and languages, from research to art to poetry, and expressed cross-media, enriching the written text with visual, video and audio contributions. The voices belong to professionals from different backgrounds. Researchers, artists, planners and curators are all featured. Together they narrate the plurality of Radical Creativities; together they explore the transformative power of cultural practices; together they declare the radical nature of creative actions.